

Kuna

also known as “Tule”, “Cuna”

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Anj Droë, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: South American Religions, Central American Religions, Religious Group

The Kuna, whose name for themselves is “Tule,” are an indigenous Central American group living along the northern coast of Panama. Originally from the Gulf of Urabá in present-day Colombia, the Kuna fled Spanish occupation in the 17th century and settled in what is now the Darién Province of Panama, eventually relocating to their current location on the San Blas Islands and northern coast. Through a combination of strategic alliances, negotiation, and rebellion, the Kuna have managed to maintain much of their cultural and political identity in the face of colonial pressure to assimilate. This entry focuses on ethnographic evidence collected during fieldwork with the Kuna shortly after 1925, when La Revolución Tule (the Kuna Revolution), in response to assimilation pressure, won the Kuna semi-autonomous status for their land. During this time, traditional Kuna religion was still practiced, although syncretism with Christianity, and in particular Protestantism, was present. Living a righteous life, so as to avoid angering the supreme high god Pab Dummat, was of central importance in Kuna religion. The righteous were rewarded in the afterlife and wrongdoers were punished. Considerable political and religious overlap appears to have been present both in community leaders and in ceremonies. For example, large religious singing or chanting ceremonies took place in the same community meeting houses used for political purposes. Because religious beliefs were inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large.

Date Range: 1912 CE - 1937 CE

Region: San Blas Archipelago ca. 1927

Region tags: North America, Mesoamerica and the Caribbean

San Blas Archipelago, Panama, ca. 1927

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sb05-021>

- Source 1 Description: Holmer, Nils Magnus. 1951. "Cuna Chrestomathy." In *Etnologiska Studier*, Vol. 18:191. Göteborg: Etnografiska Museet.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sb05-005>
- Source 2 Description: McKim, Fred, and Henry Wassén. 1947. "San Blas: An Account of the Cuna Indians of Panama ; the Forbidden Land : Reconnaissance of Upper Bayano River, R.P., in 1936 : Two Posthumous Works." In *Etnologiska Studier*, Vol. 15:186. Göteborg: Etnografiska Museet.
- Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sb05-008>
- Source 3 Description: Nordenskiöld, Erland. 1930. "Cuna Indian Religion." In *Proceedings of the International Congress of Americanists*, Vol. 23:668-77. New York: [s.n.].
- Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sb05-001>
- Source 1 Description: Nordenskiöld, Erland, Ruben érez Kantule, and Henry Wassén. 1938. "An Historical and Ethnological Survey of the Cuna Indians." In *Comparative Ethnographical Studies*, vol. 10:xxvii, 686 , plates. Göteborg, Sweden: Göteborg Museum.
- Source 2 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sb05-003>
- Source 2 Description: Stout, David Bond. 1947. "San Blas Cuna Acculturation: An Introduction." In *Viking Fund Publications in Anthropology*, 124 , plates. New York: [s.n.].
- Source 3 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=sb05-000>
- Source 3 Description: Tice, Karin E. (Karin Elaine), and Ian Skoggard. 1999. "Culture Summary: Kuna." New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Those Scotchmen, Englishmen and Frenchmen must have had considerable influence upon the culture of the Cunas. . . . The religion they heard about was not only Catholicism but also Calvinism, and traces of this are met with in present-day Cuna religion" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:3).

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: "Their [the Kuna's] latest revolt [against the Panamanian government] was as recent as 1925" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:668c).

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: "Their [the Kuna's] latest revolt [against the Panamanian government] was as recent as 1925" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:668c).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: "Their [the Kuna's] latest revolt [against the Panamanian government] was as recent as 1925" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:668c).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), internal warfare among the Kuna is rated 1.25, which is between "Internal warfare seems to be absent or rare (original code 1)" and "Internal warfare seems to occur once every 3 to 10 years (original code 2)" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), external warfare among the Kuna is rated 1.5, which is between "External warfare seems to be absent or rare (original code 1)" and "External warfare seems to occur once every 3 to 10 years (original code 2)" (Ember and Ember, 1992; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Ethnographic evidence also indicates the presence of external warfare: "The latest occurrence worthy of note in the history of [the Kuna] was when, in 1925, a considerable section of the tribe, after instituting a massacre on all Panamanians within their territory, proclaimed the independent republic of Tule, whose flag is a blue swastika on orange ground with red borders" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:6).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Membership is consequently assumed to be assigned at birth.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Because religious beliefs are inseparable from almost all aspects of social and political life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society itself. Therefore, it is assumed that the religion has political support.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 757, Political and Religious Differentiation, "There is considerable overlap between political and religious leaders" (Ross, 1983; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 20100

Notes: "Year Population . . . 1925 estimated 20,100" (Stout, 1947:50-60).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of religious leaders called Néle and medicine men. See Nordenskiöld, 1930:670a-b for more information.

Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that both Néle and medicine men possess supernatural powers. See Nordenskiöld, 1930:670a-b for more information.

Powers are inherited:

– Yes

Notes: "In contradistinction to the ordinary medicinemen, a person is born Néle. This office is not attained merely by passing through a course of instruction" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:670b).

Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: "One becomes an Inatulédi [medicine man] by studying under some established medicineman" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:670a).

Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: "An Inatulédi is just an ordinary medicineman--or even, though more rarely, a medicine woman--who collects medicinal plants and other medicines, and who, assisted by the tutelary spirits, undertakes to search for souls that have been carried off by evil spirits" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:670a). "A Néle is . . . is a very wise man--or occasionally a very wise woman--who has made important discoveries, who is learned in the history of the Cuna tribe, who, in cases of illness can indicate the cause, and who possesses the power of recovering lost property" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:670b).

Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: "In contradistinction to the ordinary medicinemen, a person is born Néle. This office is not attained merely by passing through a course of instruction" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:670b).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of cemeteries: "Those of the Cuna who occupy the coral islands of the San Blas Archipelago have their burial grounds on the mainland. Each family there possesses a hut in which their dead are buried. These huts constitute the village of the dead [cemetery]" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:675c).

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: "Those of the Cuna who occupy the coral islands of the San Blas Archipelago have their burial grounds on the mainland. Each family there possesses a hut in which their dead are buried. These huts constitute the village of the dead [cemetery]" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:675c).

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: "Nowadays nuchus [powerful wooden figurines hosting a spirit that helps religious specialists find lost purbas or souls] and kapoletis [staffs similar to nuchus] are a conspicuous trait in Cuna culture, for not only are they an essential part of the equipment of every innatuledi and nele [religious specialists] but they are also one of the few examples of representative art [referred to as tutelary spirits]" (Stout, 1947:102-103a).

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: "Many of [the tutelary spirits] exhibit two outstanding features; the knees are bent and the clothing depicted is of European style, including an 18th century uniform, nun's habit, and modern suits" (Stout, 1947:102-103a).

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: "The Cuna Indians carve from . . . wood and sometimes from liana vines, figures [tutelary spirits] which . . . are always in the form of human beings" (Nordenskiöld et al.,

1938:345).

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: "Many of [the tutelary spirits] exhibit two outstanding features; the knees are bent and the clothing depicted is of European style, including an 18th century uniform, nun's habit, and modern suits" (Stout, 1947:102-103a).

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of sacred places called piryas or piryagana, in which wild animals and spirits live and humans are unable to go. See Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:15-16 for more information.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of sacred places called piryas or piryagana, in which wild animals and spirits live and humans are unable to go. See Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:15-16 for more information.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Before speaking any further of [demons], I ought to mention that the Cuna differentiate between body and soul. The latter is able to leave the body, as, for instance, during sleep. . . . After death the soul departs from the body and is carried to the nether world by the tutelary spirits" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:673c).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: "Before speaking any further of [demons], I ought to mention that the Cuna differentiate between body and soul. The latter is able to leave the body, as, for instance, during sleep. . . . After death the soul departs from the body and is carried to the nether world

by the tutelary spirits" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:673c).

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "Before speaking any further of [demons], I ought to mention that the Cuna differentiate between body and soul. The latter is able to leave the body, as, for instance, during sleep. . . . After death the soul departs from the body and is carried to the nether world by the tutelary spirits" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:673c).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Everything in this nether world [the afterlife] is of gold or silver, gold being the metal of the righteous and silver that of the wicked" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:676).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Everything in this nether world [the afterlife] is of gold or silver, gold being the metal of the righteous and silver that of the wicked" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:676).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: "Everything in this nether world [the afterlife] is of gold or silver, gold being the metal of the righteous and silver that of the wicked" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:676).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "In the burial houses on the coast they dig a deep rectangular grave for each dead person" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:455).

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "In the burial houses on the coast they dig a deep rectangular grave for each dead person" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:455).

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: Suspended then fallen

Notes: "The dead person in the hammock thus hangs free in the burial room on the floor of which the articles he is to have with him are placed. Gradually the hammock falls down and the grave is filled up" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:455).

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↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment, "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of co-sacrifices.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "Personal articles and models of various objects are placed in the grave; over the grave are placed broken furniture and artifacts" (Stout, 1947:40).

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: "Personal articles and models of various objects are placed in the grave; over the grave are placed broken furniture and artifacts" (Stout, 1947:40).

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: "Personal articles and models of various objects are placed in the grave; over the grave are placed broken furniture and artifacts" (Stout, 1947:40).

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "Those of the Cuna who occupy the coral islands of the San Blas Archipelago have their burial grounds on the mainland. Each family there possesses a hut in which their dead are buried. These huts constitute the village of the dead [cemetery]" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:675c).

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "Those of the Cuna who occupy the coral islands of the San Blas Archipelago have their burial grounds on the mainland. Each family there possesses a hut in which their dead are buried. These huts constitute the village of the dead [cemetery]" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:675c).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic indicates the presence of a supreme high god and multiple non-human supernatural beings. See questions below for details.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, a supreme high god is "present, active, and specifically supportive of human morality" (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 34).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: "In the picture writing he [the supreme high god] is represented in human form" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:671).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: "God came from under the earth for himself. And then he stood up from under the earth and he started to thought himself how to make a woman" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:440).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Yes

Notes: "God came from under the earth for himself. And then he stood up from under the earth and he started to thought himself how to make a woman" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:440).

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "We cannot conceal ourselves from him [god]. He knows everything" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:435).

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: "We cannot conceal ourselves from him [god]. He knows everything" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:435).

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: "We cannot conceal ourselves from him [god]. He knows everything" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:435).

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: "We cannot conceal ourselves from him [god]. He knows everything" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:435).

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Notes: "The god of the Cuna is not the god of all peoples, but only their own god" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:671a).

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: "We cannot conceal ourselves from him [god]. He knows everything" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:435).

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: "We cannot conceal ourselves from him [god]. He knows everything" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:435).

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: "We cannot conceal ourselves from him [god]. He knows everything" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:435).

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: "We cannot conceal ourselves from him [god]. He knows everything" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:435).

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "He [the supreme high god] is still intervening in the affairs of men; he inflicts punishment upon transgressors" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:671a).

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– No

Notes: "He [the supreme high god] does not help people directly but only by means of what he has created for their protection" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:436).

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "He [the supreme high god] is still intervening in the affairs of men; he inflicts punishment upon transgressors" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:671a).

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "He [the supreme high god] does not help people directly but only by means of what he has created for their protection" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:436).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the supreme high god is considered wrathful. See Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:436 for more information.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– No

Notes: "It is never said of him [the supreme high god] that he visits mankind on earth; never that the medicinemen speak with him, nor that they obtain assistance from him in their incantations" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:671).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that previously human spirits can be summoned from the afterlife: "It is not permissible to mention the name of a deceased person. This goes to show that it is possible to summon the dead, although they be far away in the nether world" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:673-674). However, it appears that previously human spirits are generally not involved with the affairs of the living: "They [the Kuna] have nothing at all to do with the purba [spirit] of the newly departed. Therefore it appears that the Cunas, in contrast with the majority of other Indians, do not fear them" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:357).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Demons are everywhere present" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:674a).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "But the demons frequently assume animal shape" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:673c).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "In this nether world [the afterlife] are many custodians [demons], some of whom, as, for example, those who cause the rain to fall, take an active part in the earthly life of man" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:670d).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: ". . . the Cuna imagine that when a person has fallen ill, the illness is due to his soul having been carried off by an evil spirit . . ." (Nordenskiöld, 1930:675b).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic indicates the presence of a supreme high god and multiple non-human supernatural beings (demons). See questions below for details.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: "The Cunas recognize a superior power in natural manifestations. They believe that the orderly progression of phenomena is due to a directing head. Since this directing head, God, created people in the world, they reason that God possesses human attributes" (McKim and Wassén, 1947:92).

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: "They [non-human supernatural beings] are found in the winds, in the sea, in plants and animals, and in the eight layers of which the earth is built up" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:674a).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "It is further their [the Kuna's] belief that . . . there is a nether world where the righteous will be rewarded and evil-doers be punished" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:670d).

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "It is further their [the Kuna's] belief that . . . there is a nether world where the righteous will be rewarded and evil-doers be punished" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:670d).

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: "At every point the dead man is confronted by perils that may destroy him if he has led a sinful life, that is to say, if he has been guilty of adultery or stealing" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:676).

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: "At every point the dead man is confronted by perils that may destroy him if he has led a sinful life, that is to say, if he has been guilty of adultery or stealing" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:676).

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: "It was God who punished mankind by means of the flood, among other things, because people had begun to use obscene language, had become dishonest, and no longer believed in him" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:671a).

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: "At every point the dead man is confronted by perils that may destroy him if he has led a sinful life, that is to say, if he has been guilty of adultery or stealing" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:676).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that supernatural beings mete out punishment in the current life and in the afterlife. See Nordenskiöld, 1930:670d-671a for more information.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that punishment is meted out by the supreme high god and be supernatural beings in the afterlife. See Nordenskiöld, 1930:670d-671a for more information.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that punishment is meted out by the supreme high god and be supernatural beings in the afterlife. See Nordenskiöld, 1930:670d-671a for more information.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that punishment is meted out by the supreme high god and be supernatural beings in the afterlife. See Nordenskiöld, 1930:670d-671a for more information.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "It is further their [the Kuna's] belief that . . . there is a nether world where the righteous will be rewarded and evil-doers be punished" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:670d).

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: "Of demons he [the deceased] sees none, but, on the other hand, there are ferocious beasts who will annihilate him if he has sinned whilst on earth" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:676).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "He [the supreme high god] is still intervening in the affairs of men; he inflicts punishment upon transgressors" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:671a).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: "It was God who punished mankind by means of the flood, among other things, because people had begun to use obscene language, had become dishonest, and no longer believed in him" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:671a).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: "It is further their [the Kuna's] belief that . . . there is a nether world where the righteous will be rewarded and evil-doers be punished" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:670d).

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "It is further their [the Kuna's] belief that . . . there is a nether world where the righteous will be rewarded and evil-doers be punished" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:670d).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: "The mythology of his people, as related by Chief Nele Kantule, includes a number of super beings who dwelt on the earth in olden times. Ibeorgun, who brought God's word to men was such a one. Ibelele, another, was a great teacher and an advocate of moral living. Other super-mundane characters lived on high mountains. Their name is legion" (McKim and Wassén, 1947:93).

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that messianic figures were present in the past: "This was explained to them by Ibeorgun, a superman who was a friend of God and dwelt among men in the earliest days" (McKim and Wassén, 1947:92). See McKim and Wassén, 1947:92-93 for more information.

↳ Coming has already passed:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that messianic figures were present in the past: "This was explained to them by Ibeorgun, a superman who was a friend of God and dwelt among men in the earliest days" (McKim and Wassén, 1947:92). See McKim and Wassén, 1947:92-93 for more information.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: "Ibeorgun, who brought God's word to men was such a one. Ibelele, another, was a great teacher and an advocate of moral living" (McKim and Wassén, 1947:93).

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: "Ibeorgun, who brought God's word to men was such a one. Ibelele, another, was a great teacher and an advocate of moral living" (McKim and Wassén, 1947:93).

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "In the opening address, the chief reminded the women of how Papa (i. e., God) has created the river (where the women work) and that it is necessary for them to live in peace and harmony with each other and with their husbands and children, in order that Papa may continue to give them good things" (Holmer, 1951:17a).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group. See Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:92-95, 226, 269-273 for more information.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: "He [Ibeorgun, a historical leader viewed as a messiah] is even the great moralist, who exhorts the people to keep peace with each other, to honor their father and their mother, to have respect for the old, to be honest and so on" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:226).

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: "He [Ibeorgun, a historical leader viewed as a messiah] said: You ought to love those close to you and your enemies" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:273).

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: "He [Ibeorgun, a historical leader viewed as a messiah] is even the great moralist, who exhorts the people to keep peace with each other, to honor their father and their mother, to have respect for the old, to be honest and so on" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:226).

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: "These modesties, plus hospitality, generosity with one's food and drink, and consistent consideration for others, are essential aspects of the ideal personality in San Blas Cuna society" (Stout, 1947:48a).

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: "He [Ibeorgun, a historical leader viewed as a messiah] is even the great moralist, who exhorts the people to keep peace with each other, to honor their father and their mother, to have respect for the old, to be honest and so on" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:226).

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: "He [Ibeorgun, a historical leader viewed as a messiah] is even the great moralist, who exhorts the people to keep peace with each other, to honor their father and their mother, to have respect for the old, to be honest and so on" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:226).

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Notes: "Aside from the strong sex attitudes of modesty noted on earlier pages, one should also be modest regarding his own achievements—a braggart, especially one who fabricates, does not inspire confidence among his fellows" (Stout, 1947:48a).

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Humane treatment of animals

Notes: "... the Cunas forbid maltreatment of dogs and other animals ... " (Nordenskiöld et al., 1947:388).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: "When the medicine man goes for medicines in the forest or gives them to a sick person he may not sleep with a woman because then the plant spirits, who are women, will be jealous and will go away and the medicine will be worthless" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:344).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: "When the medicine man goes for medicines in the forest or gives them to a sick person he may not sleep with a woman because then the plant spirits, who are women, will be jealous and will go away and the medicine will be worthless" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:344).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: "The animals whose meat we should eat are: uedar, sule, yanu, yarmoli [tapir] kuini [squirrel], nu [pigeon], sigli [wild turkey], kuama [pheasant], but we should not eat sule kaynu [lowland paca], nor obsulu, ukusulu, nor tidi [different kinds of monkeys]" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:275).

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: "During the first year a girl's nose and ears are pierced, as are occasionally a boy's" (Stout, 1947:34b).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: "Prayers and sacrifices are unknown" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:650).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: "Prayers and sacrifices are unknown" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:650).

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: "Prayers and sacrifices are unknown" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:650).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: "Prayers and sacrifices are unknown" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:650).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: "Prayers and sacrifices are unknown" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:650).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "Communities alternate political meetings in the local congresos [village assembly] with singing gatherings where saklas and caciques [chiefs] chant religious and historical songs full of symbolism and myth, and the arkar (vocero, or chief's spokesman) interprets the meaning of the chants" (Tice and Skoggard, 1999:10).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates the presence of multiple extra-ritual in-group markers, including tattooing, piercing, ornaments, and traditional clothing.

Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: "Painting and tattooing were practiced; the designs of the latter differed according to status as well as between the various chiefs and their followers" (Stout, 1947:65-66a).

Circumcision:

– No

Notes: "Circumcision is not practiced among the Cunas so far as I know" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:30-35d).

Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: "The animals whose meat we should eat are: uedar, sule, yanu, yarmoli [tapir] kuini [squirrel], nu [pigeon], sigli [wild turkey], kuama [pheasant], but we should not eat sule kaynu [lowland paca], nor obsulu, ukusulu, nor tidi [different kinds of monkeys]" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:275).

Hair:

– Yes

Notes: "The first of the menstruation feasts when the girl's hair is cut to half length around her head, is called innamutikit; the second menstruation feast, when the hair is cut entirely off, is called innasuit or innakobet" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:57).

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: "Wini ['strings of tiny colored beads worn wrapped around the forearms and lower legs'], mola blouses ['multilayered panels of cloth cut away to reveal intricate patterns and then carefully hand stitched'], wraparound skirts, head scarves made from imported cloth, and a gold nose ring are considered 'traditional dress' for women" (Tice and Skoggard, 1999:3-4).

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: "During the first year a girl's nose and ears are pierced, as are occasionally a boy's" (Stout, 1947:34b).

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: "If the meal which they have eaten together has consisted of peccary, yānu, then they are peccary-friends, aiyānu, and by this appellation they subsequently address one another. In the same way they become tapir friends, aim[unknown]oli, if they have eaten flesh of the tapir. If they have eaten eggs, they call each other ainabdulu. It is always only one main dish that the foster-brothers [sworn friends] in this manner partake of together" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:37).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 237, Jurisdictional Hierarchy Beyond Local Community, the Kuna have one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a tribe (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas column 32).

Welfare

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The [Kuna] were asked to specify the essentials of their immediate needs [following a flood resulting in famine]. As a result thousands of pounds of shelled corn, a large quantity of sugar and salt, cans of gunpowder and bags of shot were delivered by [Panamanian] Government truck to Capitana, and turned over to the [Kuna], free of any stipulations" (McKim and Wassén, 1947:185).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: While ethnographic evidence indicates that care is given to the elderly, it does not appear to be institutionalized: "God has said that we are to respect the old; when an old man comes along the road the old man is to go first and the young one after" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:131).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: "The school in Ustúpu is a quite recently established institution. It was founded in 1930 and is now under the direction of the Cuna Indians, Samuel Morris and Frank Wilbur. They have around a hundred pupils, all boys" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:50).

Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Notes: "The school in Ustúpu is a quite recently established institution. It was founded in 1930 and is now under the direction of the Cuna Indians, Samuel Morris and Frank Wilbur. They have around a hundred pupils, all boys" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:50).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "In 1919 the first competitive examinations for scholarships were given and by 1924 there were sixty Cuna students in the city schools, the majority of them from Nargana" (Stout, 1947:89a).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: "The Congreso General Kuna created a unified political entity that can negotiate with the Panamanian government. . . . The region has three caciques (chiefs), each responsible for a particular subregion, and a regionwide intendente (administrator). Caciques are selected from Kuna leaders at the local level, whereas the intendente, until the 1990s always a non-Kuna, is named by Panama's president" (Tice and Skoggard, 1999:8).

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that the Kuna interact with both Panamanian and Colombian governments. See Stout, 1947:84-85 for more information.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: "We have also the igarsailagāna, of which there are eight to ten. It is they who have the supervision of the paths and roads. For example when the weeds have grown up too high they report this to the chief and at a meeting the work of clearing the roads is assigned to some of the men. This is carried out under the direction of the igarsailagāna" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:48).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– I don't know

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that taxes were levied only upon people with children in local schools: "The [local] schools were supported by a tax levied upon each man whose children attended and paid over to the native teacher, a young man who had been educated in Panama City" (Stout, 1947:90a).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 90, Police, the Kuna possess a specialized police force (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: "The administration of justice within the Cuna community is in the hands of not the state but the family" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:43).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: "The administration of justice within the Cuna community is in the hands of not the state but the family" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:43).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: "The administration of justice within the Cuna community is in the hands of not the state but the family" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:43).

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Ethnographic evidence indicates that written language is not present: "When we consider that there is no written language, and the exchanges by word of mouth must be carefully recorded in memory, this [greeting] custom speaks strongly for the substantial character of the Cuna, and his regard for facts" (McKim and Wassén, 1947:104a-b). However, picture writing appears to be present: "A point of great interest is that the [Kuna] possess a system of picture writing" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:669d).

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The school in Ustúpu is a quite recently established institution. It was founded in 1930 and is now under the direction of the Cuna Indians, Samuel Morris and Frank Wilbur. They have around a hundred pupils, all boys. There they learn reading, writing and arithmetic as well as some geography and history, Spanish and English" (Nordenskiöld et al., 1938:50).

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "I have met two [Kuna] who have been to Sweden and have heard of one who can speak Swedish. This may appear very strange, but it well known that not a few [Kuna] have signed on in sailing ships, many of which probably were Scandinavian, and then sailed round the world" (Nordenskiöld, 1930:669b).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Days of the week are ordered and named as follows: "Sunday Pigeon day: the day on which a 'kwanur pigeon' arose (or appeared) at Kalarwana Thunder day: the day on which much thunder was heard Tarpon day: the day on which a man was carried off by a tarpon Louse day: the day on which a louse waked up a man (from his sleep) Jaguar day Saturday" (Holmer, 1951:129-131b-c). See Holmer,

1951:129-131a for more information on the naming of months and periods of the year.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society itself, this entry assumes that the religious group provides food for itself. The Kuna depend primarily on small-scale agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation), with fishing (SCCS Variable 205, Dependence on Fishing) as a secondary means of subsistence. Hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) supplements the diet (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: The Kuna depend primarily on small-scale agriculture (SCCS Variables 207, Dependence on Agriculture, and 232, Intensity of Cultivation), with fishing (SCCS Variable 205, Dependence on Fishing) as a secondary means of subsistence. Hunting (SCCS Variable 204, Dependence on Hunting) supplements the diet (Murdock, 1962-1971; retrieved from Divale, 2004. Note: equivalent to Ethnographic Atlas columns 7 and 28).